

Screening and Identification of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* VUR 102 for Antibacterial Activity, Isolated from Lake Hussain Sagar, Hyderabad, India

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Abstract -Antimicrobial resistance in bacteria is one of the main causes of deaths due to infectious diseases. So, there is an acute need for the production of new antibacterial agents to combat infectious diseases. Bacteria are very diverse and not explored fully. It is well known that bacteria are the best producers of antimicrobial metabolites as they are very versatile in having less generation time and can be genetically modified, with no ethical limitations. Moreover, metabolites produced by bacteria are very diverse in their structure and function as the bacteria which produce them tolerate various types of stresses for survival. So, the present study focuses on the antibacterial activity of bacterial isolates, identification of the potent bacterial isolate using morphological, biochemical, enzymatic, cultural and molecular methods of identification. The results revealed that one of the bacterial isolates, which was identified as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* VUR 102 is a potent producer of antibacterial metabolites, as it exhibited good antibacterial activity against Gram positive and Gram negative test bacterial cultures, evident from highest zones of inhibition. So, the isolate *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* VUR 102 was selected for further research work.

Keywords: Antibacterial resistance, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, Screening, Identification, National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), 16S rRNA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Among the varied problems of mankind, emerging infectious diseases (EIDs) have become one of the ineluctable concerns, as they affect global economy and public health [1]. Besides this, antibiotic resistance makes it onerous to treat some infections. This is evident in Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), which has even made the existing antibiotics helpless. Other bacteria like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and *Escherichia coli* cause infections that are hard to control [2,3]. In case of nosocomial infections and in immunocompromised patients, the bacterial infections can be easily established and are very hard to be controlled [4,5,6]. Considering these facts, there is an acute need for new antimicrobial agents to combat antibiotic-resistant bacterial pathogens [7].

Antibacterial compounds of microbial origin (especially of bacteria) are the best solution for many problems, as bacteria are very versatile in having less generation time, compared to other microbes and are predominantly studied for new bioactive compounds [8]. In addition, strain improvement of bacteria can be done easily to bring about necessary changes in the final product. Search for new antibiotics, which are effective against multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogenic bacteria is an important aspect of antibiotic research [9,10]. So, the present study focuses on the isolation, screening and identification of bacteria, capable of producing antibacterial compounds to control bacterial pathogens. Few bacterial genera like *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* that are capable of living in harsh environments can be the best sources for isolating potent bacteria that can produce antibacterial agents to compete with other bacteria in their vicinity for food and space [11,12].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

The water samples were collected from different points of Hussain Sagar Lake, Hyderabad, India. The samples collected were of 30cms depth, where water ripples move frequently. Samples were collected in clean glass containers, brought to the laboratory and processed immediately.

Maintenance of test bacterial cultures

Bacterial cultures used for testing antibacterial activity were procured from The Microbial Type Culture Collection and Gene Bank (MTCC) at Institute of Microbial Technology, Chandigarh, India. The bacterial cultures include both Gram-positive bacteria (*Micrococcus luteus* MTCC 106, *Arthrobacter protophormiae* MTCC 2682, *Rhodococcus rhodochrous* MTCC 265, *Lactobacillus acidophilus* MTCC 10307, *Enterococcus faecalis* MTCC 439 and *Streptococcus mutans* MTCC 497) and Gram-negative bacteria (*Alcaligenes faecalis* MTCC 126, *Enterobacter aerogenes* MTCC 10208 and *Proteus vulgaris* MTCC 426). These cultures are grown on Nutrient agar medium slants and were maintained in the refrigerator [13].

Isolation of bacteria

Water samples were gently shaken and made 10-fold serial dilutions. The samples (0.1ml) from 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} and 10^{-7} were spread on the sterile nutrient agar plates (triplicates) aseptically using a sterile glass spreader. Then, the plates were incubated in the incubator at 37°C for 24 hours for the formation of colonies [14].

Colony characters

The 19 bacterial isolates obtained in the process of isolation were sub-cultured and maintained on Nutrient agar medium to study their colony characters like shape, colour or pigment, margin and elevation [15].

Gram's staining

All the bacterial isolates were actively grown on nutrient agar medium and their microscopic features like Gram's nature, cell shape and arrangement of cells were observed under the microscope after performing Gram's staining [16].

Screening for Antibacterial activity by Agar well diffusion method

The pure cultures of all the obtained bacterial isolates were grown individually in nutrient broth medium for 120 hours and centrifuged to remove the bacterial cell mass. Then, the cell free broth was extracted using ethyl acetate and the obtained ethyl acetate extract was stored for further use. Test bacterial cultures were freshly sub-cultured on Nutrient agar medium slants and grown for 24 hours. Bacterial culture suspension was aseptically prepared by adding sterile distilled water to 24 hour old cultures. Nutrient agar medium was prepared and each of the bacterial suspensions was added separately to molten state agar medium, following the pour plate method and allowed the plates for solidification of the medium. After the solidification, wells were made in agar plates using 6mm cork borer. Then, 100 μ l of ethyl acetate extract was added aseptically to the wells in triplicates and were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours [17]. All experiments were performed in triplicates wherever applicable. The mean and standard deviation of triplicate measurements were determined using Microsoft Office Excel for all antibacterial activity data.

Identification of bacteria

Bacterial isolate that exhibited better antibacterial activity than all other isolates, against test bacterial cultures, by exhibiting better zone of inhibition, was selected for the identification. The isolate was also grown on special bacterial growth media like cetrinide agar medium to study the cultural characters to identify it. Moreover, the isolate was grown in nutrient broth medium and 24 hours actively growing culture was used for hanging drop method to study the motility of the bacterial isolate.

Routine biochemical tests like Indole, Methyl Red, Voges-Proskauer and Citrate (IMViC) tests were performed to understand the isolate's metabolism. In addition, few enzymatic tests useful for identification like catalase and oxidase tests were carried out. Furthermore, sugar fermentation tests were carried out to find if the isolate was able to ferment different sugars and if it was able to produce acid or acid and gas. The selected isolate was also subjected to molecular studies to confirm the identity of the isolate [18,19].

Molecular identification

The selected bacterial isolate was renamed and the confirmation of the tentatively identified bacterial isolate was done by 16S rRNA gene sequencing, to confirm its identity up to species level. The sequence was then analysed using BLAST (Basic Logical Alignment Search Tool) program to find similar sequences from GenBank of NCBI. The closest similarity was found and the taxonomic relatedness of the isolate was figured out, followed by construction of phylogenetic tree by Maximum Likelihood method and Neighbor-Joining method [20]. The evolutionary analysis was conducted in MEGA7 to clearly represent the close genetic relationship among living organisms [21,22]. The 16S rRNA gene sequence of the confirmed isolate was deposited in GenBank of NCBI to obtain a unique accession number.

III. RESULTS

Isolation of bacteria (Colony morphology on nutrient agar medium)

After the incubation of inoculated nutrient agar medium plates, 19 representative bacterial isolates were obtained. The bacterial isolates exhibited varied colony characters when grown on Nutrient agar medium as presented in the table-1.

Table-1: Colony characters of bacterial isolates on Nutrient agar medium

S.No.	Isolate	Shape	Colour	Margin	Elevation
1	VUR 2.1	Irregular	Blue-green pigment	Curled	Convex
2	VUR 2.2	Circular	White	Entire	Flat
3	VUR 2.3	Circular	Dirty white	Curled	Raised
4	VUR 2.4	Circular	Yellow	Entire	Flat
5	VUR 2.5	Irregular	Creamy yellow	Undulate	Flat
6	VUR 2.6	Circular	White	Entire	Raised
7	VUR 2.7	Circular	Translucent	Entire	Flat
8	VUR 2.8	Circular	White	Entire	Umbonate
9	VUR 2.9	Irregular	White	Lobate	Flat

10	VUR 2.10	Irregular	White	Rhizoid	Flat
11	VUR 2.11	Circular	Yellow	Entire	Raised
12	VUR 2.12	Irregular	White	Lobate	Flat
13	VUR 2.13	Circular	Red	Entire	Raised
14	VUR 2.14	Filamentous	White	Filamentous	Flat
15	VUR 2.15	Circular	Creamy yellow	Entire	Convex
16	VUR 2.16	Irregular	Translucent	Lobate	Flat
17	VUR 2.17	Circular	White	Lobate	Flat
18	VUR 2.18	Circular	Creamy yellow	Entire	Flat
19	VUR 2.19	Irregular	Brown	Entire	Umbonate

Gram's staining

Of the 19 isolates, 11 isolates were found to be Gram positive bacteria and the rest were Gram negative bacteria. Thirteen isolates were found to be bacilli (rods) and rest all were found to be spherical (cocci) in shape. The cell arrangement of the bacterial isolates was found to be bunches of cocci (staphylococci), chains of cocci (streptococci), single rods, dual rods (diplobacilli) and chains of rods (streptobacilli) (Table-2).

It was found that among the monobacilli (single rods), there were 5 Gram negative and 2 Gram positive bacteria. Among diplobacilli, 2 Gram positive rods were found. There were 4 Gram positive streptobacilli, 1 gram negative streptobacilli and 2 Gram positive staphylococci were found.

Table-2: Gram's nature, cell shape and cell arrangement of bacterial isolates

S. No.	Isolate	Gram's nature	Shape	Arrangement of cells
1	VUR 2.1	Negative	Bacilli	Monobacilli
2	VUR 2.2	Positive	Cocci	Staphylococci
3	VUR 2.3	Positive	Bacilli	Diplobacilli
4	VUR 2.4	Negative	Bacilli	Streptobacilli
5	VUR 2.5	Negative	Bacilli	Monobacilli
6	VUR 2.6	Positive	Cocci	Streptococci
7	VUR 2.7	Negative	Bacilli	Monobacilli
8	VUR 2.8	Positive	Cocci	Staphylococci
9	VUR 2.9	Negative	Bacilli	Monobacilli
10	VUR 2.10	Positive	Bacilli	Streptobacilli
11	VUR 2.11	Negative	Bacilli	Monobacilli

12	VUR 2.12	Negative	Cocci	Diplococci
13	VUR 2.13	Positive	Bacilli	Diplobacilli
14	VUR 2.14	Positive	Bacilli	Streptobacilli
15	VUR 2.15	Positive	Bacilli	Streptobacilli
16	VUR 2.16	Positive	Bacilli	Monobacilli
17	VUR 2.17	Positive	Cocci	Monococci
18	VUR 2.18	Negative	Cocci	Monococci
19	VUR 2.19	Positive	Bacilli	Monobacilli

Figure-1: Antibacterial activity of the bacterial isolates against test bacteria

Screening for Antibacterial activity

Out of 19 bacterial isolates, 6 isolates namely VUR 2.1, VUR 2.4, VUR 2.5, VUR 2.11, VUR 2.16 and VUR 2.17 exhibited better antibacterial activity against most of the test bacteria (Figure-1). One of the isolates, VUR 2.1 exhibited higher antibacterial activity than all other isolates (13.67 ± 0.58) against *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. Moreover, all the test bacteria were inhibited by the isolate VUR 2.1. It was also observed that the isolate VUR 2.5 has shown antibacterial activity only against 3 test bacteria. The isolate VUR 2.16 has shown the least antibacterial activity against *Enterobacter aerogenes* (7.0 ± 0) and against *Rhodococcus rhodochrous* (7.33 ± 0.58). Except the isolate VUR 2.4, all the other isolates inhibited the growth of all Gram negative test bacterial cultures. When compared to Gram negative test bacteria, Gram positive bacteria were found to be more sensitive to all the bacterial isolates. It was remarkable that the isolate VUR 2.1 exhibited better antibacterial activity than standard antibiotic Gentamycin against *Lactobacillus acidophilus* (13.67 ± 0.58) and *Alcaligenes faecalis* (13.00 ± 0.00). Some images showing antibacterial activity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* VUR 2.1 are given in the plate 1.

Plate-1: Agar well assay method showing Antibacterial activity of VUR 2.1 against test bacteria

Against *Lactobacillus acidophilus*

Against *Arthrobacter protophormiae*

Against *Enterococcus faecalis*

Against *Alcaligenes faecalis*

Against *Streptococcus mutans*

Identification of bacteria

To identify the bacterial isolate that exhibited good antibacterial activity (VUR 2.1), morphological, cultural, biochemical, sugar fermentation tests and molecular methods were employed. On Gram's staining, the bacterial isolate VUR 2.1 was found to be Gram negative and rod shaped bacterium (Table-2).

Cultural characters of the isolate VUR 2.1

When grown on nutrient agar medium, luxurious growth was observed with blue green pigment production and metallic lustre was seen. Also it was found that the pure culture plates exhibited grape juice like odour, which is the characteristic feature of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* indicating that the isolate can be *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

In addition, the isolate was grown on cetrimide agar medium, which is the selective medium for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and was found that the growth was luxurious and the pigment production was intensified with metallic lustre on cetrimide agar medium (Figure-2). Moreover, the hanging drop method confirmed that the isolate VUR 2.1 was a motile bacterium.

Figure-2: |Growth of the isolate VUR 2.1 on Nutrient agar medium and Cetrimide agar medium

Biochemical tests of the bacterial isolate VUR 2.1

Biochemical tests were performed for the isolate, VUR 2.1 and was tentatively found as *Pseudomonas* sp. It was observed that the isolate exhibited negative result for Indole, Methyl red, Vogues-Proskauer and citrate utilization tests. Furthermore, the isolate was tested for catalase and oxidase enzymes, both catalase and oxidase enzymes were positive for the isolate as shown below (Table-3 and Figure-3).

Table-3: Biochemical characteristics of the isolate VUR 2.1

S. No.	Biochemical and Cultural Tests	Result
1	Indole test	Negative
2	Methyl Red test	Negative
3	Vogues Proskauer test	Negative
4	Citrate Utilization test	Positive
5	Oxidase	Positive
6	Catalase	Positive

Figure-3: IMViC, Catalase and Oxidase tests of the isolate VUR 2.1

Sugar fermentation tests of the bacterial isolate VUR 2.1

From the sugar fermentation tests of the bacterial isolate VUR 2.1, it was found that the bacterial isolate was able to utilize fructose, sucrose, glycerol, maltose, mannitol and starch. Also it was found that acid and gas were produced during the fermentation process which was evident from colour change of the medium and the presence of air bubble in the Durham's tubes in all the sugars which were utilized (Table-4 and Figure-4).

Table-4: Sugar fermentation tests of the bacterial isolate VUR 2.1

S.No.	Sugars	Acid production	Gas production
1	Glucose	Negative	Negative
2	Fructose	Positive	Positive
3	Sucrose	Positive	Positive
4	Lactose	Negative	Negative
5	Glycerol	Positive	Positive
6	Maltose	Positive	Positive
7	Mannitol	Positive	Positive
8	Cellulose	Negative	Negative
9	Starch	Positive	Positive
10	Control	Negative	Negative

Figure-4: Sugar fermentation tests of the bacterial isolate VUR 2.1.

1. Glucose, 2. Fructose, 3. Sucrose, 4. Lactose, 5. Glycerol, 6. Maltose, 7. Mannitol, 8. Cellulose, 9. Starch and 10. Control

Identification of the bacterial isolate renamed as VUR 2.1 by 16S rRNA gene sequencing

One of the bacterial isolates that exhibited potent antibacterial activity among all other isolates, VUR2.1 was renamed as VUR 2.1, was tentatively identified as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, based on Gram's staining, cultural and biochemical tests. The further confirmation of the bacterial identity was done based on the molecular identification method. The 16s rRNA gene sequences were analysed using BLAST (NCBI), the isolate VUR 2.1 was found to be closely related to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The evolutionary history of the bacterial isolate was inferred and a phylogenetic tree was drawn as given in the figure-5.

Figure-5: Molecular Phylogenetic analysis of the isolate VUR 102 by Maximum Composite Likelihood (MCL) approach.

The sequence of the bacterial isolate renamed as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* VUR 102 was submitted to NCBI GenBank and the accession number given by NCBI GenBank was PQ864776.

IV. DISCUSSION

One of the challenges in the medical science is controlling antibiotic resistance in bacteria. To handle this crisis, search for new antimicrobial agents in these days is of great demand [23,24,25]. Search for new antibiotics has led to the discovery of thousands of antibiotics during few decades [26]. Generally, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* proves to be ubiquitous as it has the ability to survive in environment, where very scarce nutrients are present. It can grow simply on distilled water, waste water, tap water, soil or even in the moist environment [27,28]. Due to these special features, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* can thrive in any harsh environment and can be very competitive to other bacteria by showing its antagonistic properties [29,30].

It is very clear from the above results that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* VUR 102 is considered as the best of all the isolated bacteria, as it showed better zone of inhibition against most of the test bacteria. The identification of the bacterial isolate was very convincing and clear, right from its isolation, as the isolate showed its colony characters like blue-green pigment production and the medium plates were diffused with its pigment, Metallic lustre like appearance on Cetrimide agar, showing Pyocyanin which is the characteristic feature of *Pseudomonas* [31,32,33]. In addition, Gram's staining, biochemical tests, enzymatic tests and sugar fermentation tests done in the process of identification have given a clear indication that the bacterial isolate is *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Furthermore, the bacterial isolate was subjected to molecular identification by 16S rRNA gene sequencing, which confirmed the identity of the isolate as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

V. CONCLUSION

From the above findings, it can be concluded that the isolate VUR 102 was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (GenBank Accession number PQ864776). It can be inferred that the bacterial isolate is a producer of potent bioactive metabolites, that are capable of exhibiting antibacterial activity. So the isolate was selected for further studies like optimization, mass production of bacterial culture, extraction of the metabolites, purification and identification of the bioactive principle.

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